

29 strong coupling is ubiquitous and determinative for the dynamics. A hallmark example
30 is conical intersections (CIs)^{4,5}, ultrafast gateways between different potential energy
31 surfaces (PESs), efficiently converting electronic into vibrational excitation. CIs govern
32 many vital processes, for instance, the retinal isomerization⁶ of the vision process and
33 the photo-stability of DNA bases⁷. The experimental challenge^{6,8-24} is the simultaneous
34 tracing of the electronic and nuclear motion on the intrinsic ultrafast timescale²⁵⁻²⁷ and
35 following the system's radiation-less decay across transient and, often, optical dark
36 states²⁸.

37 Here, we meet these combined challenges with attosecond core-level absorption
38 spectroscopy: A 165-as-duration attosecond soft x-ray (SXR) pulse provides the ultrafast
39 temporal resolution to resolve even the fastest coherent electron dynamic events while,
40 at each instant of time, due to its broad and coherent bandwidth of more than 300 eV,
41 covering the whole (carbon C(1s)) absorption edge region, signatures of the electronic
42 states and nuclear dynamics are encoded at different energetic positions in the
43 absorption spectrum. We will show that the method's intrinsic element specificity and
44 electronic-state selectivity – combined with the ultrafast temporal resolution, allow us
45 to trace and identify the various contributions from single atomic sites of the molecule.
46 While attosecond core-level absorption spectroscopy generally applies to gas-phase,
47 liquid, or solid-state systems alike, we here demonstrate its efficacy as a powerful new
48 analytic tool by identifying and tracking the entire ring-opening dynamics of furan. We
49 time-resolve the various nonadiabatic transitions across the CIs of the system and
50 identify the electronic and nuclear coherences, electronic and vibrational frequencies,
51 and their decay.

52

53 We chose to investigate furan (C_4H_4O) since it serves as a prototypical system for
54 heterocyclic organic rings^{29,30}, which are essential building blocks of polymers, fuels,
55 pharmaceuticals, atmospheric constituents, organic electronics, and light-harvesting
56 systems, agrochemicals, and more. Thus, their photochemical dynamics and relaxation
57 processes are of great interest³¹ for various applications. The results of our investigation
58 demonstrate that attosecond core-level spectroscopy³²⁻⁴² is a powerful analytical
59 technique to elucidate complex chemical reaction dynamics.

60

61 Attosecond core-level spectroscopy provides information on unoccupied electronic
62 states via dipole-allowed core-level transitions; thus, the method is sensitive to optically
63 dark states to UV/VIS transient absorption methods, which play a crucial role in many
64 reaction pathways. With sufficient screening between the core and valence states, core-
65 level transitions provide a non-ambiguous mapping between the measured photons and
66 the probed electronic states. This is critical for the clear identification of electronic and
67 nuclear effects³⁶.

68

69 The relevant electronic states of photo-excited furan are shown in Fig. 1a. Due to the
70 stark difference of dipole transition moments, infrared photons at 0.7 eV (1850 nm)
71 excite the molecule predominantly in the Franck-Condon (FC) region from its electronic
72 ground state (GS) to the $\pi\pi^*$ (S_2) excited state (see Supplementary Sec. S5.2).
73 Theoretical investigations^{29,43-45} have discussed two competitive pathways along which
74 furan evolves after such photoexcitation into the S_2 state: (i) The molecule can evolve
75 after $\pi\pi^*$ excitation via nonadiabatic passage through the $(\pi\pi^*)/(3s)$ crossing and
76 $(\pi\pi^*)/S_0$ conical intersections back to the initial GS (S_0). This pathway leads to distortion

77 of the nuclear framework out of the molecular plane, called ring-puckering (RP). (ii)
78 Alternatively, ring-opening (RO) occurs via 3 CIs: $\pi\pi^*$ excitation in the FC region
79 proceeds through the first CI ($\pi\pi^*$)/($\pi 3s$) from S_2 to S_1 , then through the second CI
80 ($\pi\pi^*$)/($\pi\sigma^*$) upon which S_1 changes its character from $\pi\pi^*$ to $\pi\sigma^*$. The anti-bonding $\pi\sigma^*$
81 state is dissociative, thus leading to the fission of the C-O bond. At the ring-opened
82 geometry, the system further relaxes through the ($\pi\sigma^*$)/ S_0 conical intersection to the
83 electronic ground state. Both pathways⁴⁶ lead to strong vibrational excitation.

84 Previous experimental studies employed single-photon and strong-field excitation to
85 trace these pathways. For instance, photoemission experiments successfully identified,
86 yet with contradicting outcomes, the photoproducts of RP^{47,48} or RO⁴⁹ in furan and
87 inferred branching ratios⁵⁰ and diabatic passage⁴² through a CI, but with insufficient
88 resolution to identify and track the predicted electronic dynamics. Another study with
89 time-resolved Coulomb explosion imaging identified RO as end product⁵¹. A recent
90 investigation with ultrafast electron diffraction on cyclohexadiene⁵² only revealed the
91 end product of conformational change. Femtosecond x-ray absorption spectroscopy on
92 furfural⁵³ identified the chemical shift and population of PES, but it could not resolve
93 electronic coherences or vibrational excitations upon diabatic passage. Thus far, despite
94 encouraging progress^{40,53,54}, identifying the ultrafast pathways with their expected
95 electronic and vibrational coherences has been obscured by the challenge of temporally
96 resolving and directly spectrally identifying them^{19,55}. Even more so, the evolution of the
97 coupling of electronic and vibrational dynamics in real-time has been largely elusive.

98 Here, we meet this challenge by IR-pump, attosecond SXR probe spectroscopy of gas-
99 phase furan inside a 4-mm-long effusive cell with 400-micron entrance and exit holes

100 for pump and probe beams. 17-fs-duration, carrier-envelope phase stable pump pulses
101 at 1850 nm (0.7 eV) with intensity up to 47 TW/cm² excite furan. This intensity yields
102 photo-excited but neutral furan molecules. The ionization fraction at the pump intensity
103 amounts to a negligible 2.5%, based on RT-TDDFT calculations (see Supplementary Sec.
104 S5). The attosecond SXR pulse interrogates photo-excited furan in transmission by
105 measuring the x-ray absorption near-edge spectra (XANES) with a homebuilt SXR
106 spectrometer with $dE/E \sim 1/1000$ resolution at the carbon K-edge at 284 eV. See the SI
107 for details.

108 Before detailing the temporal reaction dynamics, we highlight the sensitivity of XANES
109 to orbital symmetries: For instance, in the GS, the molecule exhibits C_{2v} symmetry, i.e.,
110 only 2 of the 4 carbon atoms are symmetry distinct. This symmetry arises from the
111 different binding of the two sets of carbon atoms (C₁ and C₂) and sensitively registers as
112 two energetically shifted core transitions into the dipole-allowed lowest unoccupied
113 molecular orbital (LUMO), C_{1,2}(1s)→π*, in the x-ray absorption spectrum. Figure 1b
114 shows the measured static (un-pumped) XANES, in which the signatures of the two
115 distinct carbon atoms are visible as double peaks around 285.6 eV and 286.5 eV. Further
116 visible in the edge region, above the two LUMO peaks, are contributions from transitions
117 into the Rydberg and σ* states and higher order and mixed π* states.

118

119 We now turn to investigate the dynamics of photo-excited furan and will extract its time
120 evolution from the pump-probe measurement. Figure 2a shows the measured
121 differential absorption spectrum, which displays the changes in the XANES relative to
122 un-excited (ground-state) furan. In the following, we will use the combination of
123 experiment and theory to elucidate the evolution of the furan system. We focus on the

124 temporal features and pre-edge spectral region while providing a complete spectral
125 analysis in Supplementary Sec. S6. Our theoretical methods include RT-TDDFT, coupled
126 cluster singles and doubles calculations⁵⁶ to calculate the XANES spectra, and for the
127 excited-state dynamics, semi-classical ab-initio on-the-fly surface-hopping dynamics,
128 including nonadiabatic and laser couplings⁵⁷; see the Supplementary Sec. S5 and S8 for
129 detailed information.

130

131 **Excitation and coherent electronic wave packet dynamics**

132

133 Figure 2a shows that the pump-probe overlap region features very rich dynamics. The
134 analysis of this region is typically avoided due to averaging over field-driven dynamics
135 and excitations by the pump and probe fields with varying waveform structure⁵⁸. Here,
136 in contrast, we employ CEP-stable fields, thus providing confidence, in combination with
137 ab-initio RT-TDDFT simulations, to extract the dynamics. The simulations include all
138 relevant electronic states and the pump-field-driven electronic dynamics without
139 assumption on dipole matrix elements; see Supplementary Sec. S5 and Supplementary
140 Fig. 7 for the ionization and occupation dynamics. The extensive theoretical treatment
141 by different methods and the comparison of several of its features with experiment
142 identifies excitation into neutral furan's $\pi\pi^*$ (S_2) state during the pump-probe overlap.
143 We also found that one-photon oscillator strengths describe the same excitation step
144 well, thus simplifying the theoretical description with the semi-classical surface hopping
145 method. The optical excitation of one electron from the doubly occupied highest
146 occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) into the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital
147 (LUMO) by the pump pulse creates a singly occupied molecular orbital (SOMO) which

148 registers as a new absorption peak at 282 eV in the differential absorption spectrum
149 below the static absorption edge (285 eV), see also Fig. 2b, orange line. Subsequent
150 dynamics are inferred from analyzing the time evolution of different energetic
151 signatures above the edge region. Immediately apparent in Fig. 2a at early delay times
152 are strong modulations in the differential absorption spectrum, both positive (red) and
153 negative (blue), and across the entire shown photon energy range. We identify strong
154 modulations in the differential absorption spectrum at 287 eV and 289.4 eV (signal
155 region “I” and “II”), which we show as a lineout in Fig. 3a. The two differential absorption
156 curves reveal rapid modulations at a frequency of 63 ± 9 THz, corresponding to a period
157 of 16 fs; see inset in Fig. 3a. The time-frequency analysis reveals the coherent oscillations
158 frequency and shows that the signal starts at 20 fs, i.e., at after the pump pulse; see Fig.
159 3b. Interestingly, further analysis reveals that these modulations are out-of-phase to
160 each other and dampen after about 80 fs; see Fig. 3b and Supplementary Sec. 7 and
161 Supplementary Fig. 18c.

162

163 To elucidate the origin of this behavior, Fig. 4a shows the calculated population
164 dynamics within the first electronic excited states. The remarkable agreement with the
165 measurement allows us to explain the observed behavior: we find from the semi-
166 classical dynamics that already after 12 fs, the $\pi\pi^*$ population traverses the $(\pi\pi^*)/(\pi 3s)$
167 conical intersection. Passage through the conical intersection couples these electronic
168 states and establishes a fixed phase relation between the two evolving populations,
169 manifesting in quantum beats due to the intrinsic electronic coherence; see
170 Supplementary Sec. S7. The measured beat frequency of 63 ± 9 THz is in excellent
171 agreement with theory, which predicts 60 ± 6 THz for RO and 62 ± 9 THz for RP; see Fig.

172 4c. Simulations further confirm the dephasing of the coherence after 60 fs due to the
173 different dispersion of PES, in good agreement with the value of 80 fs from the
174 measurement.

175

176 Further, the coherent electronic motion of charge density across the two distinct carbon
177 atoms of furan exhibits a π -phase shift between the spatially separate nuclear sites. We
178 show them as red and green insets in Fig. 3a and Supplementary Fig. 18c. Such out-of-
179 phase oscillations of electronic quantum beats have been theoretically predicted⁵⁹ but
180 have never been experimentally detected. They register via the complex transition
181 dipole matrix element of the core-transition to the common final (valence) state as anti-
182 phase evolution of quantum beats at the two energies distinct for the two carbon sites.
183 Our measurement provides the first site-specific tracking of the coherent wavepacket
184 evolution across the molecule's nuclear structure and clocking of the electronic
185 coherence between different states. The electronic quantum beating is predominant in
186 spectral regions "I" and "II" as in these spectral areas, the two involved valence states
187 S_1 and S_2 have a common final state in the x-ray absorption. See Supplementary Sec. S7
188 for a detailed discussion.

189

190 **Vibronic excited state dynamics at 2nd conical intersection**

191 Following the dynamic evolution of the coherent mode at 63 THz, we observe a
192 switchover after 80 fs to a lower-frequency mode at 36 ± 9 THz (Fig. 3b). This mode
193 decays after 140 fs. Semi-classical dynamic simulations show that the nuclear wave
194 packet passes through another conical intersection, $(\pi\pi^*)/(\pi\sigma^*)$, after around 58 fs for
195 the RO pathway. This passage changes the S_1 state's electronic character to an optically

196 dark dissociative $\pi\sigma^*$ state (see Supplementary Sec. S6). The appearance of the 36 ± 9
197 THz frequency mode originates from coherent vibrational motion along the dissociative
198 state as vibrational quantum beating. A normal mode analysis on the ensemble of
199 trajectories allows ready identification of the 37 THz mode for the RO pathway (see Fig.
200 4d, Supplementary Sec. S11). This event arises due to C-O bond fission. The measured
201 decay of the 63 THz mode is explained by dephasing the coherent electronic wavepacket
202 motion due to the rapidly increasing energy separation between PES (Fig. 4b). The
203 stretching of the nuclear framework destabilizes the S_2 and S_3 PES while stabilizing S_1
204 (see Fig. 1a). Our combined theoretical and experimental analysis shows that non-
205 adiabatic passage through the $(\pi\pi^*)/(\pi\sigma^*)$ conical intersection along the RO pathway
206 results in a change of the electronic character to the optically dark dissociative $\pi\sigma^*$ state
207 after 58 fs resulting in a change in the frequency from 63 THz to 36 THz. This change is
208 accompanied by the dephasing of the coherent electronic wave-packet motion due to
209 the rapidly increasing energy separation of electronic states on the RO trajectory (Fig.
210 4b). In fact, the increasing PES gradient of the RO trajectory results in strong
211 deformation of the nuclear framework and coherent vibrational excitation. This is visible
212 as a large chemical shift from 286.5 to 284 eV in the differential absorption spectrum
213 (region "III").

214

215

216 **Ring-opening of furan**

217

218 The accompanying observed splitting of the single SOMO peak (Fig. 2c) into 4 peaks after
219 80 fs is an unmistakable signature of ring scission due to the breakage of C_{2v} molecular

220 symmetry and of presence of electronic population in the $\pi\sigma^*$ dark dissociative state
221 (see also Supplementary Sec. S6 and S12). Further, the vibrational coherence and the
222 spectral features of the $\pi\sigma^*$ state vanish after 140 fs (Region “IV” in Fig. 2; Fig. 3 and
223 Supplementary Sec. S6). Both observations agree with the theory, predicting passage
224 along the RO trajectory through the $(\pi\sigma^*)/S_0$ conical intersection after 158 fs. Theory
225 predicts a probability of 76% for the observed relaxation channel along the RO
226 coordinate. Region “IV” shows that the SOMO peaks disappear in lieu of one peak at
227 282.5 eV; see also Supplementary Fig. 13c and d. This is in excellent agreement with the
228 simulations which predict a single LUMO peak at 282.5 eV for relaxation to the RO
229 ground state.

230

231 The described investigation and its minute identification of various signatures of
232 molecular dynamics show the power of attosecond core-level spectroscopy to reveal
233 correlated multi-body electronic and nuclear dynamics in a complex molecular system
234 on its native ultrafast timescales. Further, core-level spectroscopy is intrinsically
235 electronic state- and element-specific, permitting spatially resolving electronic and
236 nuclear wavepacket dynamics across the molecular framework. Due to the broad
237 spectral bandwidth intrinsic to attosecond SXR pulses, the entire region around an
238 atom’s x-ray absorption edge is probed coherently at every sampling delay – thus, down
239 to the attosecond timescale. The method’s particular sensitivity to coherences, phases,
240 optically dark states, and vibrational dynamics allows us to resolve and identify
241 nonadiabatic passages, changes in a system’s electronic character, and quantum beats.
242 We explain how the different observables will enable us to disentangle the entire time
243 evolution of complex coupled molecular electronic and vibrational dynamics after

244 photoexcitation. This study on furan disentangles the system's whole nonadiabatic ring-
245 opening passage by identifying all three conical intersection passages, their electronic
246 coherences with their dephasing, and relaxation to the RO ground state. For instance,
247 we identify passage through the first CI ($\pi\pi^*$)/($\pi 3s$) with concomitant electronic
248 quantum beats by the appearance of a 63 ± 9 THz signal after 20 fs (theory: 12 fs and
249 60 THz). Passage through the second CI ($\pi\pi^*$)/($\pi\sigma^*$) is detected by a rapid frequency
250 shift to 36 ± 9 THz after 80 fs (theory: 58 fs, 37 THz) and is explained by rapid electronic
251 dephasing in lieu of a nuclear coherence. Passage through the third CI ($\pi\sigma^*$)/ S_0 results
252 in termination of the 37 THz signal after 160 fs (theory: 158 fs). We note that the
253 switchover from 1 to 4 SOMO peaks is another direct signature of RO and the
254 disappearance in favor of a LUMO peak constitutes return to the new ground state of
255 the RO configuration. The investigation shows that the power of attosecond core-level
256 spectroscopy lies in the combined temporal resolution and coherent energy spectrum
257 to reveal hitherto inaccessible insight into molecular systems' real-time electronic and
258 nuclear dynamics. Armed with intricate knowledge of a molecular system's different
259 couplings and phase evolution, we expect the method provides a decisive new angle on
260 concepts of coherent control. For instance, the demonstrated insight into vibronic
261 couplings may allow arresting dephasing of electronic excitations to facilitate efficient
262 molecular reaction dynamics, to study the correlated multi-body dynamics leading to
263 isomerization, and manipulate energy relaxation dynamics.

264

265

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282

283 **Author Contributions Statement**

284 J.B. supervised the project. S.S. and M.R. performed the experiments with support from
285 J.B., A.S., H-W S. and Y-H C.; S.S. analyzed experimental data with support from M.R.,
286 J.B. and K.M.Z.; K.M.Z. performed the quantum chemical and semi-classical dynamics
287 calculations with support of S.G.; K.M.Z. and S.G. analyzed theory data; J.B. wrote the
288 manuscript with input from S.S., K.M.Z. and S.G.

289

290 **Competing Interest Statement**

291 The authors declare no competing interests.

292

293 **Figure Legends**

294

295 Figure 1. (a) Potential energy surfaces showing the RO and RP pathways and the
296 relevant electronic states. Note that the excited states S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 refer to the adiabatic
297 states and are labelled according to energy. I.e., these states change their electronic
298 configurations upon passage across the CIs. The transition to the S_2 state ($\pi\pi^*$) in the FC
299 is bright. (b) Electronic states in the FC region; the dominant bright state is shown as
300 thick solid line. (c) Vicinity of the first two CI of the RO pathway. Note the switchover of
301 electronic character of S_1 at the CI: ($\pi\pi^*$)/($\pi 3s$) (light blue circle) from $\pi 3s$ to $\pi\pi^*$. S_1
302 again changes electronic character when traversing the second CI: ($\pi\pi^*$)/($\pi\sigma^*$) (dark
303 blue circle) from when traversing from $\pi\pi^*$ to $\pi\sigma^*$. (d) Static (non-excited furan) carbon-
304 edge XANES. The measured absorption (red) and the calculated one (blue) are shown.
305 Purple and yellow vertical lines indicate spectral contributions from the two symmetry-
306 distinguishable carbon atoms (C_1 and C_2). The prominent peak at 286 eV originates from
307 transitions from the two non-symmetry-equivalent carbon atoms to the lowest
308 unoccupied molecular orbital, LUMO ($C(1s)\rightarrow\pi^*$). Further shown are contributions to
309 higher-lying electronic states, such as Rydberg states, anti-bonding σ^* , and higher order
310 π^* states (indicated as 1); see also Supplementary Sec. S4.

311

312 Figure 2. (a) Differential attosecond-resolved XANES measurement. The 17-fs pump
313 pulse is indicated, whose envelope is centered at "0" delay time. Further shown are
314 areas "I"-IV," which facilitate discussion of different spectral contributions in the text.
315 Substantial changes in absorption around zero delay time are observed, followed by
316 various modulations to varying frequencies due to electronic and vibrational
317 coherences. (b). Time-integrated lineouts of the sub Δ OD trace (see Supplementary Sec.
318 S3) across the energy range of (a) during the pump pulse and (c) after relaxation to the
319 $\pi\sigma^*$ state along the RO pathway. This corresponds to lineouts of the differential
320 attosecond-resolved XANES measurement from which we subtracted the overlap and
321 long-lasting features that obscure the dynamics. A singly occupied molecular orbital

322 (SOMO) peak at 282 eV, orange line, (b) in the pre-edge region, below 285 eV, indicates
323 $\pi\pi^*$ excitation. Carbon-oxygen bond fission (RO) breaks the C_{2v} symmetry, and,
324 consequently, the excitation across 4 distinct carbon atoms (C_1 - C_4) registers as splitting
325 of the singly occupied molecular orbital (SOMO) peak into 4 absorption peaks (c). See
326 Supplementary for details.

327

328 Figure 3. (a) Lineout data from the differential XANES (Fig. 2a) at two distinct energies
329 (negative and positive differences), regions I and II). After the buildup of the negative
330 (yellow) and positive (blue) absorption signals, pronounced oscillations with a frequency
331 of 63 ± 9 THz are observed; see inset. This is due to coherent electronic wave packet
332 dynamics of states S_1 and S_2 , across the molecule's nuclear structure with two
333 symmetry-distinct carbon sites, leading to quantum beating in anti-phase. The relevant
334 wave packet superpositions are shown inside the red and green panels above the
335 curves. (b) A windowed Fourier analysis of the 287-eV curve in (a) reveals the time
336 evolution of frequencies. The persistence of a frequency over a time range reveals
337 coherence. In the case of furan, we find that the electronic coherence, with 63 ± 9 THz
338 beat frequency, dephases due to the buildup of coherent vibrational excitation at a
339 lower frequency of 36 ± 9 THz.

340

341 Figure 4. (a) Theoretical results show the time evolution of the relevant three excited
342 states S_1 - S_3 and the S_0 ground state. The vertical dashed lines (purple) indicate the
343 temporal locations of nonadiabatic couplings between the various PES: $(\pi\pi^*)/(\pi 3s)$ Cl
344 at 12 fs, $(\pi\pi^*)/(\pi\sigma^*)$ Cl at 58 fs and $(\pi\sigma^*)/S_0$ Cl at 158 fs. (b) shows energy differences
345 between excited electronic states for the RO (top) and RP (bottom) pathways with a
346 Gaussian smoothing based on the pump pulse width. In accord with the measurement,
347 we find a substantial divergence of ΔE_{31} and ΔE_{21} after 60 fs, explains the dephasing of
348 the electronic coherence after that time. (c) shows a windowed Fourier analysis of
349 calculated electronic coherences. The analysis reveals electronic coherence, which
350 persists about 60 fs with a 60 THz mode for RO and 62 THz for RP, respectively. A normal
351 mode analysis (d) compared to measurement shows that the RO pathway dominates
352 the dynamics. The 37.0 THz RO mode from theory is in excellent agreement with the

353 measurement of 36 ± 9 THz (Fig. 3b). Further indicated in the blue and red panels next
354 to the modes are the relevant RP and RO modes.

355

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504

505 **Methods**

506 In our experiment, a 1.8 μm carrier-envelope phase (CEP)-stable 17 fs pump with an on-
507 target peak intensity of 47 TW/cm^2 excites the furan molecule. A time-delayed, isolated

508 attosecond probe pulse (165 as) interrogates the excited-state dynamics. Both pump
509 and probe beams are focused collinearly into the sample cell filled with furan vapor.
510 State-of-the-art theoretical methods guide the experiments: the nonadiabatic excited-
511 stated dynamics is simulated via ab initio on-the-fly surface hopping, including
512 nonadiabatic and laser coupling⁵⁷. This enables sampling all possible excited-state
513 relaxation pathways without presuming reaction modes while incorporating all relevant
514 quantum and strong-field effects. For selected structures along the trajectories, x-ray
515 absorption spectra were calculated using the core-valence-separation scheme in the
516 frozen-core equation of motion model for electronically excited states on the coupled
517 cluster singles and doubles level of theory (fc-CVS-EOM-EE-CCSD)⁵⁶. More detailed
518 information, figures, and references can be found in the supporting information.

519

520 **Data Availability**

521 All data that support the plots and findings of this study are available from the first
522 author(s) and corresponding author upon request.

523

524 **Code Availability**

525 Information about the codes and scripts is found under
526 <https://zenodo.org/records/10575861> and <https://github.com/ziechys/SharcAnalysis>

527

528 **Figure 1**

529

530 **Figure 2**

531

532 **Figure 3**

533

534 **Figure 4**

